

Complexation of nickel-, cobalt- and copper(II) with L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine – Kinetic studies

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Kinetic study on the interaction of Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} with L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (L-dopa) has been carried out under first order condition as a function of pH and temperature at $I = 0.1 M$ (KNO₃). A reaction scheme consistent with the results that at pK 8.64 both amino and hydroxyl groups undergo deprotonation, has been proposed. The overall rate constants have been resolved into stepwise rate constants. The activation parameters corresponding to stepwise rate constants, to support the proposed mechanism, have been evaluated. The suggested mechanism has been further confirmed by the calculation of water exchange rate constant.

An intricate balance in the level of neurotransmitters 'acetylcholine' and 'dopamine' is required for the normal functioning of the brain¹. Both of these neurotransmitters are synthesised from L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (L-dopa) which in turn finds its use in the treatment of Parkinson's disease (dopamine deficiency). Moreover, the role of the formation of metal chelates in the storage and transport of neurotransmitters is well established². For a better understanding of the physiological and biochemical processes, it is necessary to know the mechanism of interaction. Keeping this in mind, a systematic kinetic study of complexation of L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine with Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} has been carried out.

Results and Discussion

Ni^{II}, Co^{II}-L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine complexation :
The kinetics of interaction of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine was carried out in the pH range 6.05–6.92 and 6.13–7.00, respectively. The study was restricted in this pH range to avoid hydrolysis of M^{II} to M(OH)⁺. The reactions were monitored under first order conditions by taking $[M^{II}] \gg [L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine]$.

The investigations were carried out at temperatures 20–40° (±0.05). Oscilloscope traces of concentration changes versus time were used to evaluate the values of k_{obs} (first order rate constant). The value of second order rate constant was calculated using $k_{obs} = k'_{obs}/[M^{II}]$, where M^{II} = Ni^{II} and Co^{II} (Table 1).

Table 1. Values of second order rate constants for the interaction of Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} with L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine at different pHs and temperatures

$\mu = 0.1 M$; [Ni^{II}] = $5.2 \times 10^{-2} M$, [L-dopa] = $4.50 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Co^{II}] = $5.34 \times 10^{-2} M$, [L-dopa] = $4.58 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Cu^{II}] = $2.61 \times 10^{-2} M$, [L-dopa] = $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$

Ni ^{II} -L-dopa		Co ^{II} -L-dopa		Cu ^{II} -L-dopa	
pH	$10^{-1}k_{obs}$	pH	$10^{-2}k_{obs}$	pH	$10^{-3}k_{obs}$
Temp. = 25°		Temp. = 20°		Temp. = 20°	
6.05	0.52	6.13	3.53	2.26	1.05
6.28	1.18	6.38	6.29	2.53	1.41
6.48	2.01	6.58	9.01	2.96	2.12
6.64	3.31	6.76	13.84	3.14	3.03
6.72	3.72	6.88	17.31	3.39	4.72
6.86	5.31			3.51	6.25
Temp. = 30°		Temp. = 25°		Temp. = 25°	
6.12	1.15	6.13	5.51	2.51	1.75
6.32	2.27	6.32	7.52	2.73	2.22
6.52	3.55	6.54	13.01	2.79	2.62
6.67	1.91	6.71	17.91	3.13	4.01
6.74	6.22	6.78	24.04	3.43	7.38
6.9	9.02	6.86	27.51	3.49	8.51
Temp. = 35°		Temp. = 30°		Temp. = 30°	
6.11	1.77	6.15	8.51	2.46	1.94
6.34	3.61	6.36	12.97	2.76	3.66
6.53	5.33	6.56	21.01	2.93	4.25
6.69	7.65	6.75	31.22	3.19	6.72
6.76	8.88	6.9	34.61	3.39	9.65
6.92	13.49	7	49.91	3.42	10.31
Temp. = 40°		Temp. = 35°			
6.07	2.27	6.15	12.53		
6.32	4.75	6.4	21.01		
6.5	7.21	6.6	27.51		
6.67	10.91	6.83	47.51		
6.75	12.22	6.99	66.02		
6.9	17.41				

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L-3,4-Dihydroxyphenylalanine is a tetradentate ligand having four active sites available for complexation – a carboxylate group, an amino group and two hydroxyl groups. Generally, a reaction between transition metal ion and an amino acid results in the formation of chelate. Here, two types of chelate formation are possible, between the amino and carboxylate group and between the two hydroxyl groups. Chelate formation between the amino or carboxylate and 3- or 4-substituted hydroxyl groups is stereochemically impossible.

The macrodissociation constants corresponding to four groups are 2.34, 8.64, 9.74 and 13.0 respectively³. At pK 8.64, both the amino and hydroxyl groups undergo deprotonation⁴. Therefore, unlike in earlier studies, this value cannot be assigned exclusively to amino deprotonation.

Hence, instead of macro-dissociation constants, we must consider micro-dissociation constants. The pK value (13.0), corresponding to second hydroxyl group being too high, suggests that the deprotonation of the group would not occur under our experimental conditions. Therefore, L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine can be treated as a tridentate ligand.

Equilibria between various protonated and deprotonated forms of the ligand are diffusion-controlled (rate constants of the order of 10¹¹). Therefore, these equilibria are established readily. Though monoprotonated form of the amino acids is the most predominant one in aqueous solution, other forms of the ligand are also available for complexation.

The differential form of the rate equation for the interaction of M^{II} with L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine is represented as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= -d/dt[M^{II}] \\ &= -d/dt[\text{L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine}] \quad (1) \\ &= k_{\text{obs}} \{ [\text{HO}^+\text{-NH-COOH}] + [\text{HO}^+\text{-NH-COO}^-] + \\ &\quad [\text{-O}^+\text{-NH-COO}^-] + [\text{HO-N-COO}^-] + \\ &\quad [\text{-O-N-COO}^-] \} [M^{II}] \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} \{ [H^+]^3 + K_1[H^+]^2 + K_1K_2[H^+] + K_1K_3[H^+] + K_1(K_2K_2' + K_3K_3') \} [\text{HO}^+\text{-NH-COOH}][M^{II}]/[H^+]^3 \quad (3)$$

Keeping in view, protonation-deprotonation equilibria between various forms of L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (Scheme 1) in which M^{II} reacts in a stepwise manner with triprotonated (HO⁺-NH-COOH), diprotonated (HO⁺-NH-COO⁻), monoprotonated ((HO-N-COO⁻), (-O⁺-NH-COO⁻)) and deprotonated (-O-N-COO⁻) forms was suggested. This scheme gave the best fit with our kinetic data.

Scheme 1

From Scheme 1,

$$\text{Rate} = k_{67}k_{78}k_{8,10}k_{98} \{ k_{37}K_1K_2[H^+] + k_{59}K_1K_3[H^+] + k_{48}(K_2K_2' + K_3K_3') + k_{26}K_1[H^+]^2 \} * [\text{HO}^+\text{-NH-COOH}][M^{II}]/k_{67}k_{78}k_{8,10}k_{98}[H^+]^3 \quad (4)$$

Comparing equations (3) and (4) as both represent the rate of the complexation reaction and assuming $k_{8,10} > k_{84}$, which is the case for normal substitution at high pHs, we get,

$$k_{\text{obs}} \left\{ 1 + \frac{(K_2'K_2 + K_3'K_3)}{(K_2 + K_3)[H^+]} \right\} = (k_{37} + k_{59}) + \frac{k_{48}(K_2'K_2 + K_3'K_3)}{(K_2 + K_3)[H^+]} \quad (5)$$

Plots of $k_{\text{obs}} \left\{ 1 + \frac{K_2K_2'K_3K_3'}{(K_2 + K_3)[H^+]} \right\}$ vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ were found to be linear. The values of k_{48} and $(k_{37} + k_{59})$ were evaluated from the slope and intercept, respectively, of these plots. The values of activation parameters corresponding to specific rate constants k_{48} and $(k_{37} + k_{59})$ were calculated from linear plots of $\log k$ and $\log k/T$ vs $1/T$. These values are given in Table 2.

Copper(II)-L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine complexation : Rate constant for the complexation of Cu^{II} with L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine were determined at 20, 25 and 30 (± 0.05°). The kinetic investigations were carried out at 0.1 M ionic strength and in the pH range 2.26–3.51 (to avoid hydrolysis). The values of first and second order rate constants are given in Table 1.

In the Cu^{II} systems, water loss from Cu_{aq}²⁺ is very rapid. This is because of Jahn-Teller distortion of geometry around this d⁹ cation, resulting in two relatively distant and weakly bonded water molecules in the primary hydration sphere. Therefore, of all transition metals, Cu^{II} is one of the most kinetically labile ions. Hence, even at very low pHs, it undergoes complexation with the anionic form of the ligand. Moreover, if we do not consider the anionic forms of the ligand, it is not possible to interpret the observed kinetic data.

Table 2. Values of $(k_{37} + k_{59})$ and k_{48} and their activation parameters for the complexation of Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} with L-dopa

Temp. °C	Ni ^{II} -L-dopa		Co ^{II} -L-dopa		Cu ^{II} -L-dopa	
	$(k_{37} + k_{59})$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^{-4} k_{48}$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$(k_{37} + k_{59})$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^{-5} k_{48}$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^{-3}(k_{37} + k_{59})$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^{-9} k_{48}$ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
20			2.00	1.07	0.60	7.91
25	0.00	2.39	6.00	1.22	1.00	8.27
30	0.80	2.72	15.00	1.31	1.50	8.71
35	2.00	3.11	25.00	1.41		
40	4.50	3.34				
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	136.76 ± 20.1	16.41 ± 1.34	149.56 ± 5.11	12.09 ± 0.91	68.35 ± 4.16	4.70 ± 0.98
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	187.23 ± 7.43	-122.75 ± 4.43	254.35 ± 8.32	-123.99 ± 4.18	24.62 ± 1.17	-55.94 ± 2.61

Plots of $k_{\text{obs}} \left\{ 1 + \frac{K_2 K'_2 + K_3 K'_3}{(K_2 + K_3) [H^+]} \right\}$ vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ were found to be li-

near confirming that Scheme 1 is also applicable to this complexation reaction. The values of k_{48} and $(k_{37} + k_{59})$ and corresponding activation parameters were obtained in the similar way (Table 2).

Scheme 1 and hence the rate law was corroborated with the general law of complexation which involved the rapid equilibrium formation of ion pair complex between the metal ion and ligand followed by rate-determining inter-change step,

Rate of this reaction is expressed as

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{d}{dt} [ML^{(2-n)+}] = K_{\text{os}} k_0 [M_{\text{aq}}^{2+}] [L_{\text{aq}}^{n-}] \quad (7)$$

Also, in Scheme 1 water exchange is taking place through the steps k_{37} , k_{59} and k_{48} .

Therefore, water exchange rate is written as

$$\text{Rate} = k_{37} [^-O^-NH-COO^-][M^{II}] + k_{59} [HO-N-COO^-][M^{II}] + k_{48} [^-O-N-COO^-][M^{II}] \quad (8)$$

Because $(k_{37} + k_{59}) \ll k_{48}$ (Table 2), equation (8) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = k_{48} [^-O-N-COO^-][M^{II}] \quad (9)$$

From equations (7) and (9), we get

$$k_{48} = K_{\text{os}} k_0 \quad (10)$$

The value of K_{os} ⁵ was calculated, to be 2.17 M⁻¹. Knowing k_{48} and K_{os} , the value of k_0 (water exchange rate constant) at different temperatures was calculated from equation (10). The values of k_0 for Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} at 25° found to be 1.20×10^{-4} , 5.40×10^{-4} and 3.99×10^{-9} s⁻¹ respectively.

Generally, it has been found that the rate of complexation reaction of amino acids with transition metal ions decreases due to the presence of hydroxyl group in amino acids, e.g. in hydroxy proline⁶, rate of metal substitution is less than that for proline⁷. This effect is attributed to hydrogen bonding between OH group of the ligand and water molecule coordinated to metal. In earlier studies⁸ on metal-L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine complexation, rate constants were calculated by considering macro-dissociation constants only and the pK value 8.64 was assigned exclusively to the amino group. The values of specific rate constants were found to be less than the expected ones. The difference in the values was explained on the same basis as for proline and hydroxyproline.

Using micro-dissociation constants, we found that the observed and expected values⁹ of rate constants compared well. This is explained on the basis that the two hydroxyl groups are adjacent and are involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding. Thus, hydrogen bonding does not alter the orientation of the ligand within the ion pair for the inter-change step.

The rate of complexation of metal ion with various forms of the ligand (Table 1) is found to increase in the order: Ni^{II} < Co^{II} < Cu^{II}. This is explained on the basis of difference in crystal field stabilization energy (CFSE). The loss of water molecule changes the geometry from octahedral (Oh) to trigonal bipyramidal (TBP). The difference in CFSE (Oh-TBP) for Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} are 5.73, 2.55 and 1.09 Dq, respectively, i.e. maximum in case of Ni^{II} and minimum in case of Cu^{II}. Hence, the reaction of L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine with Cu^{II} is fast in comparison to Ni^{II} and Co^{II}.

This theoretical explanation is supported by the values of activation parameters. The smaller value of ΔH_{48}^\ddagger is responsible for larger value of k_{48} for Cu^{II}-L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine complexation. The value of ΔS^\ddagger for the steps $(k_{37} + k_{59})$ is positive because it involves reac-

tion between metal ion and the monoprotonated form of the ligand. Whereas, ΔS^\ddagger value for the step k_{48} is found to be negative because it involves reaction between metal ion and the deprotonated form of ligand. This supports the proposed associatively activated mechanism.

For Cu^{II} , interaction with monoprotonated form of L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine is significant. This form of the ligand is found to be almost unreactive with other two metal ions, i.e. Ni^{II} and Co^{II} (Table 1). Physiologically, amino acids exist in monoprotonated form in body cells. When there is an excess of copper in the body (Wilson's disease), the reaction between Cu^{II} and L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (involving the formation of chelate), hinders the synthesis of dopamine resulting in deficiency of dopamine (Parkinson's disease). The low value of ΔH^\ddagger obtained, corresponding to step ($k_{37} + k_{59}$) also confirms the fact that the monoprotonated form of L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine reacts faster with Cu^{II} in comparison to Ni^{II} and Co^{II} .

Experimental

L-3,4-Dihydroxyphenylalanine (Sigma), bromothymol blue (B.D.H.), nickel nitrate, cobalt nitrate, cupric nitrate, 2,6-lutidine (all Merck) were used as such. The ionic strength of the reaction mixture was maintained at 0.1 M by the addition of calculated amounts of KNO_3 .

Kinetic measurements were performed on an Aminco-Morrow stopped flow spectrophotometer. The transmittance changes were monitored at 620 nm for Ni^{II} -L-dopa and Co^{II} -L-dopa by pH indicator method. No indicator was used for Cu^{II} -L-dopa system as the transmittance changes were large enough to be monitored directly. Radiometer pH meter (model M26, Copenhagen) was used to measure pH of the solutions. The pH of each solution was measured before and after mixing. The pH values reported in Table I are those of the reaction mixtures.

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